

Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock Return of Firms Listed In Nairobi Securities

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Abstract

Investors return guidelines to an investment decision by all investors. Stock return is affected by micro and macro-economic characteristics. Currently, it was hypothesized that firm financial characteristics; firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, shareholders concentration have an influence on stock return. Panel regression analysis was fitted on secondary data, and it was found that there was a positive and significant influence of firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, and stock return. Further, there was a positive and significant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return.

Keywords: Leverage, Liquidity, Firm Value, Financial Health, Shareholders Concertation, Stock Return

1.0 Introduction

Securities exchange acts as an avenue through which investors can gain return from their investment. Return is always the profit which investors yield as compensation for the risk which they undertake; moreover, investors are most interested with those investment opportunities which will always increase their capital (Ahmadpour & Rahmani, 2007). Whenever an investment decision is made, there are several factors which ought to be considered, but the main consideration is made on risk and return relationship. Empirical documentation on the causal influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return and if they have any effect on portfolio formation more so because investment choice is propelled by risk return relationship.

The stock return has a long dated empirical review with Sharpe (1964), Linter (1965) and Black (1972) being the earliest proponent of the Capital Asset Pricing Model (CAPM) and they perceived a stock to return to being determined by a single determinant, i.e., beta coefficient. Empirical tests proved beta coefficient had the sole explanation of stock return (Nikolaos, Dimitrios, Prodromos, & Vassilios, 2005). The validity of CAPM as a measure of stock return has faced empirical examination, critique and subsequent publications had brought forth other significant determinants of stock return such as firm capitalization, ratio of firms to book value of common equity, leverage, price to earnings ratio (Fama & French, 1993) as cited in Nikolaos, et al., (2005).

A review of past literature reveals that firm financial characteristics have attracted huge interest among corporate financial experts since there are perceived to solely or jointly influence stock returns of listed companies (Tripathy & Ahluwalia, 2015). According to Akbar & Baig, (2010) firm financial characteristics which are commonly referred to as internal or micro factors originate from financial statements which are largely prepared with managerial control and have attracted huge attention among researchers. More so firm financial characteristics have continuously shown significant influence on organizational performance and efficiency. Indeed, individual company stock return can be uniquely identified; therefore it is necessary to examine how it is affected by firm financial characteristics.

1.1 Problem Statement

The dynamic interrelationship between firm characteristics and stock market returns have an influence on current and potential investors, government policies, management of both public and private companies owing to their influence on operations costs as well as the expected return at the end of accounting cycles. Further, the primary purpose of all investment decisions is to maximize shareholders wealth which can be clearly attained by clear balance on investment, working capital, financing and dividend decisions (Al-Salamat & Mustafa 2016; Duy & Phuoc, 2016). Although theoretical view purports that firm value, financial health, liquidity, and leverage should impact stock return positively. Indeed, there is an expected co movement between firm characteristics and stock return (Ufo, 2015).

Though firm financial characteristics impact financial performance; it is of great concern to examine their influence on stock return in a specific company due to empirical inconsistencies. Past studies such as (Prodosh, 2014; Tripathy & Ahluwalia, 2015; Ufo, 2015) argued that any change on single or collective firm characteristic has a significant influence on financial performance, customer satisfaction, and organizational growth; all this will have to influence stock return. At the moment the business environment is so dynamic, competitive, new regulations, advanced technological changes which are capital intensive all these have combined demand on huge financial reorganizations which can propel massive debt financing, changes in dividend policies, and renegotiation of debt terms. In this direction, it is important to evaluate how they will influence the stock return of a given stock. In most of them have glaring shortcoming on methodological choices for example use of short-term panel data which has limited their sample size and data analysis procedures without considering diagnostic tests. It is against this the current study theoretically and empirically reviewed the literature on the causal link between firm financial characteristics and also shareholders concentration moderating effect.

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective was meant to establish the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in Nairobi Securities Exchanges. The study was guided by the following objectives:

1. To establish the influence of firm value on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchanges.
2. To determine the influence of financial health on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchanges.
3. To examine the influence of liquidity on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchanges.
4. To establish the influence of leverage on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchanges.
5. To examine the moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchanges.

1.4 Hypothesis of the Study

The study was guided by the following hypothesis:

- i. H_{01} : Firm value has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchanges.
- ii. H_{02} : Financial health has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange.
- iii. H_{03} : Liquidity has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange.
- iv. H_{04} : Leverage has no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange.
- v. H_{05} : Shareholders concentration has no significant moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of companies listed in Nairobi securities exchange.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Asymmetric Information Theory

This theory was proposed by Myers and Majluf in 1984. The theory assumes that there are variations in levels of information asymmetry between finance providers and an organization and it will always influence the finance cost charged. Indeed, internal financiers will be more informed than external financiers and this will force external equity investors to anticipate higher returns as compared to the current investors. Due to these differing information levels, there are chances of pricing differences depending on the financier information awareness.

The applications of this theory are inhibited by its inability to identify information asymmetry levels within an organization and how they impact liquidity. In fact, there are some studies which have refuted the claims as per this theory by perceiving this debt financing to have a signaling effect as per other investment decisions. This is mainly because the release of bond financing to members of the public may signal the ability of an organization to meet its financial obligations (Luigi & Sorin, 2009). This was contrasted by a study which argued that those

firms which opt for debt financing have a tendency of practicing earnings management and consequently overvaluing their corporations which may attract debt financing which an organization does not qualify. These findings were in collaboration with Vayanos and Wang (2011) who purported that there are chances of market liquidity being influenced by access to funding which would impede the liquidity of shares in the stock market. The theory is appropriate for the study since there is a need for the securities to be freely traded and any factor impeding the sale of shares ought to be evaluated. Indeed, financial markets deviate, to varying degrees, from the perfect-market ideal in which there are no impediments to trade. Trade impediments reduce the liquidity that markets offer. A large and growing literature studies market liquidity and its properties. Theoretical papers trace illiquidity, i.e., the lack of liquidity, to underlying market imperfections such as asymmetric information, different forms of trading costs, and funding constraints. Therefore, there is a need to evaluate the effect of liquidity on stock return.

2.2 Empirical Review

An investigation of the relationship between economic value added and stock return among companies drawn from Karachi Securities Exchange was carried out by Khan, Shah, and Rehman (2012) through the use of panel research design. A sample of 60 companies listed in the period of 2004 to 2010. In the study, the controlling effect of net income and operating cash flows from activities was considered. Descriptive and pooled effects analyzed the data. EVA negatively and significantly influenced the stock return. Although, the study used panel research design it fell short on examining the diagnostic tests prior to fitting the regression model.

Baybordi, Barvari, Bahramihajiabad and Sheykhlu (2013) examined the relationship between economic value added and stock return in Jordanian. Through a panel approach, systematic sampling technique was used to select 70 companies which were listed from 2004 to 2010 in Tehran securities exchange. Regression analysis revealed an inverse relationship between stock return and EVA. Although the study drew panel data, the choice of Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to analyze the data was not appropriate since the data was a panel and it was necessary to consider its time series aspect and diagnostic tests ought to have been tested.

Campbell, Jens and Jan (2011) investigated the link between financial distress and performance of distressed securities. The study modeled financial distress using both accounting and market-based measures. Further, the estimates of distress were used to examine the impact of financial distress on stock performance in periods ranging from 1981 to 2008. Results of the study revealed that distressed securities had volatile stock returns and high market beta, in addition, they underperformed safety stock by more times on market volatility and risk aversion. Although, investors were exposed to these levels of risk they were not fully rewarded since distressed securities underperformed in the long run. Distressed stocks are modeling using both accounting, and market-based measures were not appropriate since accounting was micro in nature and market-based measures were macro.

Liquidity is the determinant of how fast stock and securities can be converted into liquid cash; this speed is used as the key determinant of market thickness and thinness. Akram (2014) investigated the effect of liquidity on stock return on ten companies listed in the Karachi stock exchange from 2005 to 2010. Liquidity was operationalized as the bid ask spread, and stock return was measured using CAPM. Two stage modelling analyzed the data. The stock return was negative and significantly influenced by liquidity. The study findings were limited since they considered very few companies and for only five years; hence it was not a true representative of the study population. Moreover, the study fell short on data analysis procedure none of the regression model assumptions was tested; hence future scholars ought to consider panel diagnostic tests prior to regression analysis.

An investigation on the day long effect of liquidity on stock return was carried out in India by Tripathy and Ahluwalia (2015) during the budget reading day. The study applied both OLS and autoregressive distributed lag model (ADRL). The significant inverse influence of stock return from liquidity was reported. Its influence was rampant during the budget preparation period. It was concluded that liquidity has a vital impact on the stock return before, during and after the budget reading. These results cannot be replicated in East Africa due to the heterogeneity of economic development.

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Malaysian case to investigate the relationship between shareholder's concentration and company performance among listed companies was brought forth by Ismail (2011). In this study shareholders' concentration was operationalized as foreign, individual, government and individual ownership and company performance which were operationalized as firm value. The study adopted correlation research design; secondary data was collected from annual financial statements of all companies listed from 1997 to 2002. Classical modeling analyzed the data. Inverse and significant influence of government ownership, foreign ownership on firm value were documented. It was concluded that most of the listed companies have a preference for a concentrated business model which were deemed to be increasing shareholders value — owing to provisions by agency theory there are prospects for enhancing the effect of firm characteristics and stock return among companies listed in East Africa.

A study by Ankensgård and Vilhelmsson (2016) to investigate the ownership determinants and stock volatility in Sweden. The panel research design was applied amongst 1600 annual observations of listed companies in periods from 2000 to 2013. In the study, it was hypothesed that shareholders return volatility was assumed to be influenced by earnings uncertainty, information uncertainty, leverage, and portfolio concentration and investor base. Classical modelling analyzed the data. Inverse and significant influence of foreign ownership and stock volatility were documented. Institutional and individual shareholders had a positive and significant effect on stock return volatility. From the findings, it was concluded that shareholder's concentration has a significant contribution to stock return volatility. Although the study relied on panel data, it was paramount to note that panel data diagnostic tests were not reported.

3.0 Research Methods

Primary, secondary data was consolidated from annual financial statements for the period 2007 to 2016. Panel modelling was applied to examine the influence of firm financial characteristics and stock return as well as the moderating effect of shareholders concentration. A panel regression model was used to test the influence of firm financial characteristics on stock in Nairobi securities exchange.

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.1}$$

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1it} + \beta_2 X_{2it} + \beta_3 X_{3it} + \beta_4 X_{4it} + \beta_5 Z_{it} + \beta_6 X_{1it} Z_{it} + \beta_7 X_{2it} Z_{it} + \beta_8 X_{3it} Z_{it} + \beta_9 X_{4it} Z_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation 3.2}$$

4.0 Findings and Discussions

4.2 Descriptive Statistics for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

As shown in Table 4.1, the average firm size in Kenya was 3.24 which indicated an increase in economic value as compared to past sales. Since the minimum value was 0.04 and maximum of 19.26, this shows that most of the firms listed in NSE were profitable and maximized shareholders returns. Similar trends were observed in

Tanzania and Uganda though firms value varied mostly in Tanzania as accounted by the standard deviation of 3.63. There is a need to take necessary measures to cushion investors against volatile investment returns in Nairobi region since it may minimize investor's confidence.

The average stock return in Kenya was 2.51% with a minimum of -1.89 and maximum of 12.51. The standard deviation of stock return was 2.22 which indicated wide variations amongst companies listed in Kenya. Most of the companies listed in Kenya were financial soundness since average financial distress was 4.69 which indicated a safety zone. Skewness coefficient was 1.57 and kurtosis of 5.73 which indicated that financial health coefficient of most companies was positive. The average liquidity of listed companies was 2.55, with a maximum of 18.76 and minimum of 0.07. This indicates that most companies listed in NSE had a high frequency of their shares trading, a clear indication of a thin market. The average leverage of listed companies in NSE was 52% with a maximum of 89% and a minimum of 29%. This indicates easy access to borrowed of listed companies in NSE. Shareholders concentration averaged at 51% in NSE, with a maximum of 84% and a minimum of 30%. This shows that there is skewed shareholders concentration amongst institutional investors who are mostly majority shareholders.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

	SR	FV	FH	Liquidity	Leverage	SC
Mean	2.51	3.24	4.69	2.55	0.52	0.51
Median	2.12	2.61	3.90	2.00	0.53	0.48
Maximum	12.51	19.26	18.15	18.76	0.89	0.84
Minimum	-1.89	0.04	0.48	0.07	0.29	0.30
Std. Dev.	2.22	2.96	3.18	2.44	0.13	0.11
Skewness	1.57	1.90	1.57	3.07	0.34	0.53
Kurtosis	6.23	7.07	5.73	15.62	2.54	2.50
Jarque-Bera	426.58	654.24	364.78	4150.86	14.06	28.64
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Sum	1272.41	1639.04	2374.72	1292.39	264.12	257.10
Sum Sq. Dev.	2488.97	4414.77	5106.90	3000.83	8.32	5.98
Observations	506	506	506	506	506	506

4.3 Panel Unit Root Test for Companies Listed in NSE

As shown in Table 4.2 the null hypothesis for non-stationarity or presence of unit roots was rejected since p values were less than 0.05 for all variables. Hence, we conclude that stock return, firm value, liquidity, leverage, financial health, and shareholders concentration were all stationary at levels.

Table 4.2 Panel Unit Root Test for Companies Listed in NSE

Variable	Test	Statistic	P value
SR	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.12	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.94	0.03
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	128.46	0.02
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	254.25	0.00
FV	Levin, Lin & Chu	-10.13	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-3.70	0.00
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	169.03	0.00
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	222.50	0.00
FH	Levin, Lin & Chu	-11.53	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-2.39	0.01
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	139.11	0.00

Liquidity	PP - Fisher Chi-square	205.32	0.00
	Levin, Lin & Chu	-8.44	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-2.39	0.01
Leverage	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	142.30	0.00
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	217.04	0.00
	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.96	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-2.48	0.01
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	133.67	0.01
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	298.52	0.00
SC	Levin, Lin & Chu	-6.91	0.00
	Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-2.10	0.02
	ADF - Fisher Chi-square	123.57	0.02
	PP - Fisher Chi-square	228.11	0.00

The p -values for the Fisher tests were based on asymptotic Chi-square distribution. The LLC test is based on asymptotic normality.

4.4 Multicollinearity Test for Companies Listed in NSE

In Table 4.3, none of the tolerance limit coefficients was less than 0.1 or VIF greater than 10. Hence, there was no collinearity amongst firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage and shareholders concentration in companies listed in NSE. Hence, a joint examination of their influence on stock return was examined using regression analysis.

Table 4.3 Multicollinearity Test for Companies Listed in NSE

	Tolerance	VIF
Firm Value	0.344	2.907
Financial Health	0.406	2.462
Liquidity	0.322	3.109
Leverage	0.718	1.393
Shareholders Concentration	0.846	1.181
Mean		2.2104

4.4 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Companies Listed in NSE

Breusch-Pagan Godfrey (chi) test was adopted to examine the uniformity of error term. The null hypothesis stated that there was uniformity of error term variance against an alternative of non-uniformity. The null hypothesis was rejected at 5% level of significance for a model with and without moderation since p values were less than 0.05. Hence, we conclude that the error term was not homoscedastic; unmoderated model had chi-square of 75.23 and p value of 0.00 and moderated model had Chi-square 318.44 and p value of 0.00. The challenge was mitigated through fitting a regression model with robust standard errors (Wooldridge, 2012).

Table 4.4 Panel Heteroskedasticity Test for Companies Listed in NSE

Model	χ^2 -Value	P value
Without Moderation	75.23	0.00
With Moderation	318.44	0.00

4.5 Panel Hausman Test for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

The choice between random effects and fixed effects as estimation model was determined using the Hausman test. Hausman test was deployed with the null hypothesis that the random effects model was preferred against an alternative that fixed effects were preferred. Results shown in Table 4.5 rejected the null hypothesis with Chi square of 3.47 and p value >0.05 for the model without moderation and Chi square of 5.9692 and p value >0.05 for a model with moderation. Consequently, the most appropriate model to estimate the influence of financial

characteristics on stock return in Nairobi securities exchanges was a random effect model. Similarly, the moderating effect of shareholder's concentration was examined using a random effects model.

Table 4.5 Panel Hausman Test for Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		3.47	4	0.4825
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
FV	0.211195	0.220229	0.000154	0.4659
FH	0.107508	0.105187	0.000162	0.8551
Liquidity	0.418442	0.394936	0.000270	0.1528
Leverage	3.083610	3.188535	0.024477	0.5024

Test Summary		Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random		5.969171	9	0.7430
Variable	Fixed	Random	Var (Diff.)	Prob.
FV	0.054712	0.112192	0.002717	0.2702
FH	0.073631	0.090592	0.003205	0.7645
Liquidity	0.670356	0.560456	0.005926	0.1534
Leverage	3.6099742	3.763685	0.508130	0.8290
SC	1.341167	1.307606	0.556994	0.9641
FV*SC	0.272034	0.189933	0.008904	0.3843
FH*SC	0.046401	0.020866	0.009797	0.7964
Liquidity*SC	-0.441050	-0.296902	0.013478	0.2144
Leverage*SC	-0.798527	-0.977842	1.851519	0.8952

4.6 Pairwise Correlation Analysis for Companies Listed in NSE

Pairwise correlation analysis was adopted to examine the strength of influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in NSE. As shown in Table 4.6, there was a positive and significant influence of firm value on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\rho = 0.821$, p value < 0.05). This showed an increase in firm value is associated with an increase in stock return of listed companies in NSE. Secondly, there was a positive and significant influence of financial health on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\rho = 0.760$, p value < 0.05). Thirdly there was a positive and significant influence of liquidity on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\rho = 0.861$, p value < 0.05). Leverage had a positive and significant influence on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\rho = 0.604$, p value < 0.05). Shareholders concentration had a positive and significant influence on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\rho = 0.395$, p value < 0.05). These findings disagreed with Khan et al., (2012) and Akram (2014) who reported inverse and significant influence of firm value and liquidity on stock return respectively. The findings agreed with Campbell et al., (2011) and Acheampong et al., (2014) who reported the significant influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return.

Table 4.6 Pairwise Correlation Analysis for Companies Listed in NSE

		SR	FV	FH	Liquidity	Leverage	SC
SR	Pearson Correlation	1					
FV	Pearson Correlation	.821**	1				
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000					
	N	506	506				
FH	Pearson Correlation	.760**	.20**	1			
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000				
	N	506	506	506			
Liquidity	Pearson Correlation	.861**	.373**	.722**	1		
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000			
	N	506	506	506	506		
Leverage	Pearson Correlation	.604**	.458**	.461**	.498**	1	
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		
	N	506	506	506	506	506	
SC	Pearson Correlation	.359**	.333**	.302**	.371**	.112*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	0.011	
	N	506	506	506	506	506	506

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

4.7 Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock Return of Companies Listed Nairobi Securities Exchange

The study examined the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange. Results shown in Table 4.7, revealed that 84% of changes in stock return of companies listed in NSE was jointly influenced by firm value, financial health, liquidity, and leverage. The remaining percentage was accounted for by other factors excluded in the model. Also, the firm financial characteristics had a significant joint influence on stock return ($F = 657.89$, p value < 0.00) and at least one of the slope coefficients was non-zero.

The first hypothesis of the study stated that firm value had no significant influence on the stock return of listed companies in NSE. Results of the study revealed positive and significant influence of firm value on stock return ($\beta = 0.22$, t statistics = 9.53, p value < 0.05). This implies that a unit increase in firm value increases stock return by 0.22 while holding financial health, liquidity, and leverage constant.

The second hypothesis stated that financial health had no significant influence on the stock return of listed companies in NSE. Results of the study revealed a positive and significant influence of financial health on the stock return of listed companies in NSE ($\beta = 0.11$, t statistics = 5.31, p value < 0.05). This implies that unit increase in financial health increases stock return by 0.11 units while holding firm value, liquidity and leverage are constant.

The third hypothesis of the study stated that liquidity had no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in NSE. Results of the study revealed positive and significant influence of liquidity on stock return ($\beta = 0.39$, t statistics = 13.83, p value < 0.05). This implies that unit increase in liquidity increases stock return by 0.39 units while holding firm value, financial health and leverage are constant.

The fourth hypothesis of the study stated that leverage had no significant influence on the stock return of companies listed in NSE. Results of the study revealed positive and significant influence of leverage on stock return ($\beta = 3.19$, t statistics = 8.68, p value < 0.05). This implies that unit increase in leverage increases stock return by 3.19 units while holding firm value, financial health and leverage are constant.

$$\text{Stock Return} = -1.37 + 0.22*\text{Firm Value} + 0.11*\text{Financial Health} + 0.39*\text{Liquidity} + 3.19*\text{Leverage} \dots\dots\dots(4.1)$$

Table 4.7 Influence of Firm Characteristics on Stock Return of Companies Listed in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FV	0.22	0.02	9.53	0.00
FH	0.11	0.02	5.31	0.00
Liquidity	0.39	0.03	13.83	0.00
Leverage	3.19	0.37	8.68	0.00
C	-1.37	0.18	-7.80	0.00
R-squared	0.84	Mean dependent var		2.51
Adjusted R-squared	0.84	S.D. dependent var		2.22
S.E. of regression	0.89	Sum squared residuals		398.07
F-statistic	657.89	Durbin-Watson stat		2.14
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00			

4.8 Moderating Effect of Shareholders Concentration on Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock Return of Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

The study investigated the hypothesis that; shareholders concentration had no significant moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on the stock return of listed companies in NSE. Multiple regression was applied and study findings reported as shown in Table 4.8; 86% of variations in stock return was accounted for by firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, shareholders concentration as well as their moderated variables.

After the incorporation of shareholder concentration as the moderator, it showed that the coefficient FV*SC was 0.19; hence shareholders concentration had a positive moderating effect on the influence of firm value on stock return. The p value was greater than 0.05. This shows that the moderating effect of shareholders concentration on firm value was statistically non-significant to stock return contribution. Secondly, there was a positive and non-significant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of financial health on the stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange $\beta=0.02$. The p value was 0.91 which was greater than the 5% level of significance. Thirdly, shareholders concentration had a significant negative moderating effect on the leverage of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchanges. Although shareholders concentration had a negative significant moderating effect on liquidity, $\beta=-0.30$, t statistics = -1.18. Finally, there was the negative and insignificant moderating effect of shareholders concentration on the influence of leverage on the stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchange, $\beta=-0.98$, t statistics = -0.28.

$$\text{Stock Return} = -2.04 + 0.11*\text{Firm Value} + 0.09*\text{Financial Health} + 0.56*\text{Liquidity} + 3.76*\text{Leverage} + 1.31*\text{Shareholders concentration} + 0.19*\text{FV*SC} + 0.02*\text{FH*SC} - 0.30*\text{Liquidity*SC} - 0.98*\text{Leverage*SC} \dots\dots\dots(4.2)$$

To confirm the moderating effect of shareholders concentration, moderated and non-moderated regression coefficients were compared with marginal change of firm financial characteristics on stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchanges. If the marginalized coefficient were different with none moderated coefficients then there was moderation. This is achieved by differentiating model 4.2, partially and incorporating the average moderating value (shareholders concentration) as follows.

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta FV_{i,t}} = \beta_1 + \beta_6 SC = 0.11 + 0.19 * 0.51 = 0.2069$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta FH_{i,t}} = \beta_2 + \beta_7 SC = 0.09 + 0.02 * 0.51 = 0.1002$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta Liquidity_{i,t}} = \beta_3 + \beta_8 SC = 0.56 + 0.30 * 0.51 = 0.713$$

$$\frac{\delta y_{i,t}}{\delta \text{Leverage}_{i,t}} = \beta_4 + \beta_9 \text{SC} = 3.76 - 1.98 * 0.51 = 2.7502$$

When the above coefficients were compared with those in model 4.1 (Stock Return = -1.37 + 0.22*Firm Value + 0.11*Financial Health + 0.39*Liquidity + 3.19*Leverage), they were different which signified shareholders concentration had moderating effect on the influence of firm financial characteristics on stock return of listed companies in Nairobi securities exchanges.

Table 4.8 Moderating Effect of Shareholders Concentration on Influence of Firm Financial Characteristics on Stock Return of Listed Companies in Nairobi Securities Exchange

Variable	Coefficient	Robust Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
FV	0.11	0.12	0.98	0.33
FH	0.09	0.10	0.88	0.38
Liquidity	0.56	0.15	3.73	0.00
Leverage	3.76	1.78	2.11	0.04
SC	1.31	1.62	0.81	0.42
FV*SC	0.19	0.21	0.90	0.37
FH*SC	0.02	0.20	0.11	0.91
Liquidity*SC	-0.30	0.25	-1.18	0.24
Leverage *SC	-0.98	3.45	-0.28	0.78
C	-2.04	0.84	-2.43	0.02
R-squared	0.86	Mean dependent var		2.51
Adjusted R-squared	0.85	S.D. dependent var		2.22
S.E. of regression	0.89	Sum squared residuals		393.14
F-statistic	293.80	Durbin-Watson stat		2.15
Prob(F-statistic)	0.00			

5.0 Conclusions and Recommendations

From the findings it can be concluded that there are need firm financial characteristics, firm value, financial health, liquidity, leverage, and shareholder's concentration have co-movement with stock return. It can be concluded that the maximization of shareholders wealth increased the stock return of listed companies. Secondly, the financial health of listed companies in NSE should be monitored continuously and financial restructuring mechanisms adopted very fast to minimize loss of shareholder wealth. Shareholders concentration should be managed to owe to the fact they may be included in the decision making process, and any negative contribution would impact negatively of stock return.

References

- i. Ahmadpour A. & Rahmani F. M., (2007). *Effect of firm size and book - market value ratio on stock return (Tehran Stock Exchange). Journal of Economic Studies*,7(9)19-37
- ii. Akbar, M & Baig, H. H. Summer (2010). *Reaction of Stock Prices to Dividend Announcements and Market Efficiency in Pakistan. The Lahore Journal of Economics*, 15(1)103-125.
- iii. Akram, N., (2014). *The Effect of Liquidity on Stock Returns: An Evidence from Pakistan, IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 16(2)66-69.
- iv. Al-Salamat, W. A., & Mustafa, H.H.H., (2016) *The Impact of Capital Structure on Stock Return: Empirical Evidence from Amman Stock Exchange. International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 7(9)183-196.
- v. Ankenstgård, H., & Vilhelmsson, A., (2016). *Ownership Determinants of Stock Return Volatility*, Retrieved from <https://www.lusem.lu.se>.
- vi. Baltagi, B.H. (2005). *Econometric analysis of panel data*, John Wiley & Sons.

- vii. Baybordi, A., Barvari, F., Bahramihajiabad, T., & Sheykhlou, M., (2013). *Evaluating the Relationship between Economic Values Added and Stock Return in Companies Listed at Tehran Stock Exchange. Journal of Basic and Applied Sciences*, 3(2)1307-1311.
- viii. Black, F. (1972). *Capital Market Equilibrium with Restricted Borrowing. The Journal of Business*, 45(3)444-455.
- ix. Campbell, John Y., Jens Dietrich Hilscher, and Jan Szilagyi. 2011. *Predicting financial distress and the performance of distressed stocks. Journal of Investment Management* 9(2),14-34.
- x. Duy, N. T., & Phuoc, N. P. H., (2016). *The Relationship between Firm Sizes and Stock Returns of Service Sector in Ho Chi Minh City Stock Exchange. Review of European Studies*, 8 (4), 210 -219.
- xi. Ismail, I. (2011). *The effect of ownership concentration on company performance, African Journal of Business Management*, 7(18)1771-1777.
- xii. Khan, M. A., Shah, N. H., & Rehman, A. U., (2012). *The Relationship between Stock Return and Economic Value Added (EVA): A Review of KSE-100 Index. Retrieved from <https://ssrn.com>.*
- xiii. Linter, J. (1965). *The Valuation of Risky Assets and the Selection of Risky Investments in the Stock Portfolios and Capital Budgets. The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 47(1) 13-37.
- xiv. Luigi, P., & Sorin, V. (2009). *A Review of the Capital Structure Theories. Annals of Faculty of Economics*, 3(1)315-320.
- xv. Nikolaos G.T, Dimitrios I. M, Prodromos, C., & Vassilios, A., (2005) "The Cross Section of Expected Stock Returns: An Empirical Study in the Athens Stock Exchange", *Managerial Finance*, 31(12)58-78.
- xvi. Prodosh S., (2014) "Firm characteristics, distress risk and average stock returns". *Accounting Research Journal*, 27(2)101-123.
- xvii. Sharpe, F. W. (1964). *Capital Asset Prices: A Theory of Market Equilibrium under Conditions of Risk. The Journal of Finance*, 19(3)425-442.
- xviii. Tripathya, T., & Ahluwalia, E. (2015). *Day Long Effect of Liquidity on Stock Return: An Empirical Investigation in a Day of Political and Economic Importance in India, International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 7(10)202-214.
- xix. Ufo, A. (2015). *Impact of Financial Distress on the Profitability of Selected Manufacturing Firms of Ethiopia. Journal of Poverty, Investment and Development*, 1(6)8-15.
- xx. Vayanos, D., & Wang, J. (2010). *Liquidity and asset prices: A unified framework, working paper London School of Economics*.